

Decebalus/Δεκέβαλος (Dekébalos)/Δεκίβαλλος (Dekíballos)/Δικέβαλος (Dikébalos)=”Righteous King” or “Rightful King” in Dacian, while Deceneus/Decaeneus/Δεκαίνεος (Dekaineos)/Dicineus meant “Righteous Priest”

second draft March 15th 2024
first draft June 20th 2023

All the previous etymologies of Decebalus and Decaeneus do not convince me, therefore I propose these new etymologies.

In the glossary of Hesychios of Alexandria, we find the gloss βαλλήν (ballén)=”king”, of which the LSJ says: “probably a Phrygian word according to Hesychios, a Thurian word according to Hermesianax Hist. (apud Pseudo-Plutarch, *De Fluviorum et Montium Nominibus* (12:4)”. The title in English of that work of Pseudo-Plutarch is: *About the Names of Rivers and Mountains/On the Names of Rivers and Mountains*; the title in Greek is: Περὶ ποταμῶν καὶ ὄρων ἐπωνυμίας. “Thurian” in the LSJ quote refers to Thuria/Thouria (Θουρία), a town of ancient Messenia in Ancient Greece, situated in the eastern part of the southern Messenian plain.

From the indications (to be treated in more detail in the next edition) present, the word βαλλήν is much more likely native to Phrygian/to the Balkans and therefore dating back to when the Phrygians were in the Balkans, and not a loan from Semitic ba’al (“lord”): post-Balkanic Semitic loanwords/names in Phrygian (post-Balkanic meaning acquired after settling in Anatolia) were certainly of a rather small number.

Another possibility is an early Semitic loan into the Phrygian language (and into the Thurian Greek dialect or Thurian Pre-Greek substrate) from when the Phrygians were in the Balkans, though that would depend on when the last Phrygians left the Balkans and when the Phoenicians became established to a degree in Greece/the Aegean coast to make such a loanword likely/possible. The name of the Kabeiroi (obscure gods worshipped by some Thracians, Ancient Greeks and others) is known to likely be cognate to Semitic Kabir, “great, big, old”, and the geographically Thracian/Northern Greek toponym Abdera is known to be very likely of Semitic (Phoenician) origin.

One indication of the term βαλλήν not being of Semitic origin is the mention of a “Ballénaion mountain” ([βαλληναῖον](#) ὄρος) in Phrygia (the name of the mountain was otherwise often translated as Basilikon in Greek, rather than using the term Ballénaion, which contains the non-Greek term Ballén-): this attestation of “Ballénaion oros” is found in Pseudo-Plutarch *De Fluviorum et Montium Nominibus* 12:4. The reasoning behind my argument that a Ballénaion mountain in the language/culture of the Phrygians indicates that Ballén is a native Phrygian term should be clear, even though this attestation does not make it for certain that the word was native Phrygian.

Whether a native Balkanic term or an early loan from Phoenician into various Balkanic languages, in either of these two scenarios βαλλήν can be cognate to the -Balus of Dekebalus, Bazobalus, etc. . The -baules seen in the name of the Thracian ruler/king Kersibaules may be a variant of this Balus in one or more dialects of Thraco-Dacian.

I posit that the Deke-/Dike- portion of Dekebalus/Dikebalis (among other variants attested) is cognate with Ancient Greek δίκη which meant “justice, right, order, law” from PIE *deyk- “to point out,

to show; to speak solemnly”; despite the Centum nature of this etymology, I find it much more likely than any other theory and more likely than my previous theory which posited a derivation from PIE **d^heh₁-*, “to put, place; to do, make”¹; and so, I think that Dekebalus/Dikebalis meant “Righteous King, Just King, Rightfully King”, something of that nature.

This theory (as does my theory from June 2023) fits the theory of some scholars that Dekebalus/Dikebalis was a title acquired by Diurpaneus, with Diurpaneus (according to that theory) being the birth-name of Dekebalus; but such a propitious name as Dekebalus/Dikebalis meaning “Righteous King, Just King” or “Rightfully King” was likely given to some Dacians/Thracians at birth as well; and in fact epigraphic attestations show that Dekebalus was the name of some Dacian/Thracians before and after the life-time of the Dacian king Diurpaneus/Dekebalus.

My theory brings forth a very likely etymology for Decaeneus/Δεκαίνεος (*Dekaineos*) as well: Decaeneus/Δεκαίνεος (*Dekaineos*) was a high-priest of Dacia during the reign of Burebista (82/61–45/44 BC). He is mentioned in the near-contemporary Geographica of Strabo (written in Greek) and in the 6th-century Latin Getica of Jordanes, where he is called “*Dicineus*”. In Strabo’s account, Decaeneus is the second most powerful man among the Daco-Getic tribes and their high priest. His support for Burebista is key to the latter’s attaining and holding power over all the tribes. He succeeded to political power in a reduced area after Burebista’s death, but he does not appear to have taken the royal title. Jordanes’ account is a derivative of Strabo’s. He credits Dicineus with bringing civilization to the Goths (whom he equates with the Getae). He places him between Zeuta and Zalmoxis as second in a succession of Dacian wise men.

My theory is that Decaeneus/Δεκαίνεος (*Dekaineos*) represents:

Dek=“Righteous, Just” and/or “Rightful”

+ *Aineos* : a word that I think meant “he who speaks of high things/divine things”, cognate to Old Greek αἰνέω (*ainēō*), “I tell of, speak of”, which Pokorny suggested is from PIE **h₂ey*, “important speech”, and Pokorny was likely right about the root.

1 My previous theory, published June 20th, 2023, was that Dekebalus/Dikebalis meant “Placed (by the gods) to be leader/king”/“Made (by the gods) to be leader/king”. Both this theory from June 2023 and my new theory fit the theory of some scholars that Dekebalus/Dikebalis was a title acquired by Diurpaneus, with Diurpaneus (according to that theory) being the birth-name of Dekebalus;

and such a propitious name as Dekebalus meaning ‘Placed (by the gods) to be leader/king’, ‘Made (by the gods) to be leader/king’, or ‘Righteous King, Just King’ was likely given to some Dacians/Thracians at birth as well; and in fact epigraphic attestations show that Dekebalus was the name of some Dacian/Thracians before and after the life-time of the Dacian king Diurpaneus/Dekebalus.

This Deke-, if it comes from a root **d^heh₁-*, a root which, in two other works of mine, I have described as also carrying the root-meaning “firm, firmly” (“to set firmly, to place firmly” and/or “firmly in place”) likely still had those “firm, firmly” connotations in Dacian and Thracian: but that’s not necessary for my etymologies detailed in this work.

In terms of form, compare Dacian Deke to Old Greek θήκη (*thékē*)=“box, chest; grave, tomb; sheath of a sword”, known to be from PIE **d^heh₁-*, “to put, place”: from this root, the word θήκη (*thékē*) came to mean a receptacle, something in which something can be placed, put; so while the form Deke is close to Old Greek θήκη (*thékē*), the meanings are quite different, though from the same PIE root (a situation, of course, which is so often encountered). Compare also to Phrygian *odeketoy*: the portion ‘deket’ has already correctly been determined to derive from PIE **d^heh₁-*, “to put, place”, though in most attested inflections, this Phrygian stem has the form “dak-” (see Phrygian *daket*, *dakeran*, *dakor*, etc.), often prefixed with A or Ad-: *adaket*/*addaket*.

If PIE **d^heh₁-*, “to put, place” is the root, then, as so often happens with such roots, the “k” sound was added (suffixed, to be exact) later and thereby avoids the sibilization, as seen for example with Kalasha dyek (=“to put, place”) deriving from PIE **d^heh₁-*, “to put, place, set; to do, make”. Kalasha is a satem language.

So then Decaeneus/Dekaineos/Dicineus meant “Righteous Priest”, with the meaning “Priest” coming from the meaning “important speech” that Pokorny says was the meaning of the root in PIE.

My previous theory was that *Dek-Aineos* meant: “Speaker (of divine things) put into place (by the gods)”, or “Made to be speaker (of divine things)”. The meaning “destined to be speaker (of divine things)” I posited as well, because for example in Sanskrit *dádhāti*, which can simply mean “to put, place, set, lay in or lay on” can also mean “to destine for”².

My new theory makes Decaeneus/Dicineus quite parallel to the Hebrew anthroponym Melki-Zedek, attested in the book of Genesis and in other books of the Old and New Testaments. Melki=“King”, while Zedek=“Just, Righteous”, and the Pheonician cognate of Zedek was also a theonym which referred to a Phoenician god associated with Justice, Righteousness and the planet Jupiter, a planet that was assigned to Zeus since ancient times.

Part Two

I will now discuss in an abbreviated style three other etymologies which have been posited in the past (by others) for Decebalus.

One of the proposed etymologies is by Sorin Paliga, one by Vladimir Georgiev, and one by a person not yet identified by me. Sorin Paliga’s theory is that Decebalus means “singing dragon” with Deke- meaning “singing” and -balus meaning “dragon”. His etymology is not impossible, though I do not subscribe to it; and I should make clear that there is another “dragon/snake” etymology of Paliga’s that I agree with: namely, I agree with his theory that the ethnonym Triballi (most likely) means “three dragons” in a Thracian dialect, with Balli most likely being cognate to Romanian *balaur/bălaur*=“dragon, monster”, and Romanian *bală*=“monster; beast; animal”; and Albanian *bollë/boljë*=1) “any of various nonvenomous snakes of the families Colubridae or Boidae; 2) the glowworm; 3) (in mythology) a seven-headed serpent’s/hydra’s early form”.

I agree that Triballi most likely means “three dragons/snakes” because it fits the nature of the Triballians, as recorded in ancient sources: I will get into more detail in the next edition, for now I will point out that archaeologists have found numerous artifacts depicting snakes which are thought to very likely belong to the Triballian culture; and Thracian artifacts depicting dragons/giant serpents with three long necks topped by a head on each neck (three-headed dragons) have been found, and the triskelion has been found to be a common Triballian symbol on Triballian artifacts, instead of a four-branched swastika.

Pliny (7.2) states that, according to Isigonus, there were people among the Triballi who fascinated by their look, and destroyed those whom they gazed upon too long, especially with angry eyes: adults were more liable to be injured by them than children. This fits the connection with dragons and snakes, since European folklore and mythology is full of tales of dragons, snakes, cockatrices and basilisks whose gaze can be fatal. Also, in Ancient Greek literature, the term Triballoi (Triballi in Old Greek) was used as a comic name for barbarian gods in general: as if some of those Ancient Greek writers knew that Triballi meant “three dragons” and that Triballi referred to a strange three-headed

² If from PIE **d^heh₁-*, “to put, place”, this Dek/Deke/Dike notion in Daco-Thracian I posited in June 2023 would be directly akin to the Vedic Sanskrit notion of *dhi*, which is a sign/vision/idea that is put/placed/given by the gods, a term which particularly was used to describe inspired poetry given by/placed into the mind by/from the gods. This *dhi* derives from an extension/inflection of (or even from a directly kindred variant of) PIE **d^heh₁-*, “to put, place”. Compare this “Dhi” to the “Dike-” in the variant Old Greek attestation *Dikébalos*, and to the *Dici-* of Jordanes’ *Dicineus*.

dragon god. There was also an Irish mythical giant Balor who could kill with flashes of light from his eye or with his poisonous breath.

So the Balli of Triballi most likely, virtually certainly, did mean “dragons, snakes” in the Triballian language. But this does not mean that Balus in Dekebalus and Bazobalus (etc.) must mean “dragon, snake”: in most languages, ancient and modern, homonym and near-homonym words are common: sometimes the homonym words are cognates, but often they are unrelated. Nor do I find the Dacian Draco battle-mascot to be compelling evidence for -Balus meaning “dragon”.

As described in part one of this work, I posit that Balus in Dekebalus and Bazobalus (etc.) meant “leader, king”, and is cognate with Phrygian/Thurian βαλλήν (“king”): but even though I posit that Balus meant “leader, king”, this Daco-Thracian Balus as well as Phrygian/Thurian βαλλήν may be cognate with Triballian -Balli (“dragons, snakes”), and with Romanian balaur, bălaur, bală; and with Albanian bollë/boljë, et al., since the root could have meant “to swell, powerful” (see PIE *b^hel- “to swell up, blow” and see also PIE *bel-, “strength”), with “to swell, powerful” leading to “dragon, monster” and “king, leader” (and “dragon” would have led to “snake”). Compare how “Basilisk” derives from Basileus (“king”) but refers to a mythical snake-like dragon, so venomous that even its gaze was deadly.

Or it may be that Balus and βαλλήν are not cognate to the Balli in Triballi nor to the other dragon/monster/snake words mentioned above. Two Old Greek words thought to derive from PIE *bel, “strength” are βελτίων and βέλτερος, which both mean “better, greater”.

Deke- according to my findings/opinions/conclusions more likely did not mean “singing, to sing” as Paliga posits. Instead I posit the meanings that I described above. I will get into more detail about my conclusions in my next edition.

Vladimir Georgiev’s theory was that Decebalus was composed of a cognate of Latin decus (“ornament”), decet (“to look like, to befit”) + a cognate of Sanskrit *bala* (“strength, power”), and that the name was possibly a loanword/loaned-name from a Cenrum language, since the *k* sound would have evolved into a sibilant in a proper Daco-Moesian language. Firstly, I don’t find compelling the meaning that Georgiev posits; secondly, it requires a Centum development, which in this case is not very likely for a Daco-Moesian-Thracian language. No one has, to my knowledge, offered a Celtic etymology for Decebalus: I do not believe that Decebalus nor Bazobalus are of names of Celtic origin.

Finally, years ago I saw a theory that Decebalus means “Ten+strength”, supposed to mean “Strong as ten (men)”: this is highly unlikely, plus the proposed Sanskrit cognate *Dasabala* to my knowledge was only used in Buddhist Sanskrit writings to refer to certain ten powers of Buddhism, not to someone as strong as ten men: nor have I seen *Dasabala* as an anthroponym. And as with Georgiev’s etymology, there is that centum problem again, since the PIE root would be *dék̑m/*dék̑mt (=“ten”), which in Sanskrit is “dasa” (sibilized as per a satem language).

I reject all of these previous theories for the Decebalus and Decaeneus anthroponyms, and I think Deke/Dike/Dek/Dik in these Dacian names derives from PIE *deyk̑- “to point out, to show; to speak solemnly”.

Alexandru Gheorghiu
June 20th, 2023
And March 15th, 2024